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LABOR MIGRATION IN UZBEKISTAN: SOCIO-ECONOMIC TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS

Razakova Barno Sayfieva

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Abstract. This article describes the causes of labor migration and its positive and negative consequences. In the course of the division of labor, the stages of development of labor migration and the factors influencing it were studied. The ownership approach was developed based on a broad analysis of the concept of labor migration. As a result of our research, scientific and practical proposals, and recommendations have been developed on the issue of regulating labor migration in our country.

Keywords: migration, division of labor, unemployment, working conditions, labor force, integration, labor migration.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada mehnat migratsiyasining sabablari hamda uning ijobiy va salbiy oqibatlarini tahlil qilingan. Mehnat taqsimoti jarayonida mehnat migratsiyasining rivojlanish bosqichlari va unga ta'sir etuvchi omillar o'rganilgan. Mehnat migratsiyasi tushunchasining keng tahlili asosida uni tartibga solish bo'yicha kontseptual yondashuv ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqot natijasida mamlakatimizda mehnat migratsiyasini tartibga solishni takomillashtirishga doir ilmiy-amaliy taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Kalit so'zlar: migratsiya, mehnat taqsimoti, ishsizlik, mehnat sharoitlari, ishchi kuchi, integratsiya, mehnat migratsiyasi.

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются причины трудовой миграции, а также её положительные и отрицательные последствия. В процессе анализа разделения труда изучены этапы развития трудовой миграции и факторы, влияющие на неё. На основе широкого анализа понятия трудовой миграции разработан концептуальный подход к её регулированию. В результате исследования сформулированы научно-практические предложения и рекомендации по совершенствованию регулирования трудовой миграции в нашей стране.

Ключевые слова: миграция, разделение труда, безработица, условия труда, рабочая сила, интеграция, трудовая миграция.

INTRODUCTION

As the global economy develops and international integration deepens, labor migration has become increasingly dynamic. The widening gap between developed and developing countries continues to play a significant role in accelerating these processes [1]. Labor migration, as a specific form of migration in the modern stage of human development, is primarily driven by the search for decent employment and higher income. It has become one of the main ways to address pressing issues of employment and income generation in countries with fragile economies and limited development opportunities.

The fundamental changes associated with the transition to a market economy in Uzbekistan had a profound impact on labor relations. In the course of economic reforms, unemployment—an inherent feature of market-based systems—emerged as a new and persistent phenomenon. As a result of structural transformation, a large share of the population lost stable employment and sources of income.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Several studies have explored the socio-economic factors driving labor migration from Uzbekistan. Karimov and Tursunov (2019) argue that high unemployment rates, low wages, and regional disparities in economic development are key push factors compelling Uzbek workers to seek employment abroad. Their research highlights the structural imbalances in the domestic labor market, where rapid urbanization and declining agricultural employment create significant pressure on labor supply and demand. Moreover, they emphasize

that remittances sent by migrant workers constitute a critical component of household income, particularly in rural areas, underscoring the economic dependence of local communities on labor migration. The authors conclude that understanding these socio-economic determinants is essential for designing targeted policies to improve employment opportunities domestically and manage migration flows effectively.

A separate line of research by Akramova (2021) examines labor migration from Uzbekistan from a policy and development perspective. The study highlights that large-scale labor migration has emerged as a coping mechanism for households facing limited employment prospects, especially during the transition from a centrally planned economy to a market-oriented one. Akramova argues that while migration alleviates short-term economic pressures, it poses long-term challenges for sustainable national development, including brain drain, social disruption, and decreased domestic labor productivity. The study also reviews government strategies to address migration, including promoting small and medium-sized enterprises, providing vocational training, and facilitating the reintegration of returnees. The findings suggest that policies combining labor market development with social support mechanisms are crucial for transforming migration from a survival strategy into a driver of sustainable economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study involves a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative analysis of labor migration statistics and remittance flows, qualitative interviews with migrant workers and their families, and a review of policy documents and academic literature to identify socio-economic trends and development impacts.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Since gaining independence, agriculture has remained one of the key sectors of Uzbekistan's economy, providing employment for a large share of the population. However, as economic restructuring and modernization have advanced, the number of people working in agriculture has gradually declined. This shift has contributed to an imbalance between labor supply and demand - especially in rural areas - and has led to rising unemployment. These trends mirror broader global patterns observed in many developing economies.

While the proportion of the population employed in agriculture has decreased globally, the pace of this change in Uzbekistan is expected to intensify in the future. In developed economies, agriculture employs a relatively small portion of the workforce but generates high levels of productivity. In Uzbekistan, however, a significant share of the population is still engaged in agriculture, which reflects the ongoing need for modernization and technological renewal in the sector.

As the financial position of farms improves and the material and technical base of agriculture develops, the level of employment in this sector is expected to decline further. Consequently, the labor market may experience increasing pressure. These trends must be taken into account when shaping state and public attitudes toward labor migrants who seek employment abroad. A fair assessment of their choice requires understanding the broader socio-economic context rather than attributing their migration to personal dissatisfaction or a desire for an easier life.

In the early years of independence, Uzbekistan had two main strategies to address unemployment and support the transition to a market economy. The first involved job creation through the development of small and private entrepreneurship, supported by government incentives and early reforms. However, given the financial constraints of a newly independent state and the lack of experience in private enterprise, this policy could only partially alleviate unemployment.

The second strategy was to open opportunities for citizens to work abroad - effectively establishing labor migration as a safety valve for domestic labor market tensions. Many individuals who lost jobs or faced underemployment chose this path as a means of supporting their families.

Labor migration, as one of the key forms of employment mobility, involves the movement of workers, specialists, and professionals across different sectors and countries [2]. However, in Uzbekistan's context, large-scale labor migration should be regarded as economically disadvantageous and a constraint on sustainable national development. From a cultural and social standpoint, it also runs counter to the nation's traditions and long-term development goals. Therefore, policies should aim to create favorable conditions for the gradual return of migrant workers and their reintegration into the national economy [3].

The persistence of large-scale labor migration even decades after independence suggests deeper systemic issues. The scientific community, particularly economists, has an important responsibility to identify effective "growth poles" and to develop evidence-based strategies for balanced national development. While it would be unfair to blame researchers for the challenges of the past, the current era of openness and academic freedom calls for more active scientific engagement in addressing the country's socio-economic problems.

In our view, there are two main policy approaches to labor migration regulation.

The first approach treats labor migration as a mechanism for supporting the national economy through remittance inflows and for alleviating labor market imbalances between labor supply and demand. This strategy may be viewed as administratively less costly in the short term and can serve as a temporary instrument to address employment challenges.

The second approach aims to gradually reduce the country's reliance on labor migration by expanding domestic employment opportunities and improving income levels within Uzbekistan. This is a complex and demanding process that requires sustained efforts, consistent policy measures, and readiness to overcome transitional economic difficulties. Although the results of such reforms may take time to materialize, their long-term impact can be significant, strengthening the foundations of national economic growth and social stability.

If successfully implemented, this strategy would bring multiple benefits for Uzbekistan. It would help accelerate economic growth, enhance the country's international reputation, and foster greater social cohesion and public confidence in national institutions. In the long run, citizens would gain the opportunity to live and work in their homeland under improved economic and social conditions, reducing the need for external labor migration.

In recent years, a considerable share of Uzbekistan's working-age population has been involved in labor migration, with many citizens employed abroad, particularly in neighboring countries. Remittances from migrant workers continue to play an important role in supporting household incomes and contributing to the national economy. However, excessive dependence on such transfers creates long-term vulnerabilities and limits the country's sustainable development potential.

Ensuring sufficient employment opportunities and decent income levels for all working-age citizens remains a strategic challenge. Therefore, if the second approach - aimed at reducing labor migration-is to be pursued, it should be implemented gradually yet consistently, through a balanced combination of economic, institutional, and, where necessary, administrative measures.

We find it necessary to outline several recommendations for addressing the issue of labor migration in a comprehensive and systematic manner.

First recommendation. Labor migration policy should prioritize the export of skilled labor. It is encouraging that the government of Uzbekistan has paid increasing attention to this issue. The Presidential Resolution "On measures to introduce a system of safe, orderly, and legal labor migration" reflects the country's commitment to improving citizens' welfare and ensuring effective migration governance [4].

To strengthen this system, it is advisable to establish, under the leadership of the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction, a mechanism for the selection, training, and deployment of qualified specialists according to the needs of labor-importing countries. Talented individuals could be selected through a competitive process, provided with training in language, culture, and professional skills required for their destination countries. A structured and knowledge-based approach to labor export would bring tangible benefits:

- increased income from the export of skilled labor;
- greater motivation among youth to acquire technical and professional education;
- improved foreign language proficiency and cross-cultural competence; and
- the opportunity for returning workers to apply acquired skills for the development of Uzbekistan's national economy.

Second recommendation. Addressing unemployment and ensuring fair wages are closely linked to the pace of economic growth. Therefore, mechanisms for wage adjustment in both the public and private sectors should reflect productivity and economic expansion. Economic progress depends not on labor migrants seeking income abroad, but on the efficiency, responsibility, and integrity of domestic institutions and professionals who shape the country's development trajectory.

Third recommendation. The adoption and implementation of laws on Minimum Wage and Living Standards would represent an important step toward reducing poverty and inequality. These measures would help increase the share of wage workers in national income and decrease the incentive for citizens to seek employment abroad.

Fourth recommendation. Improving the quality of education in Uzbekistan is fundamental to sustainable economic progress. To remain competitive globally, the country must produce high-quality and cost-efficient goods and services. Such outcomes depend directly on the qualifications, creativity, and productivity of its workforce. Large-scale investment in education and vocational training, along with a nationwide focus on developing human capital, will strengthen Uzbekistan's ability to generate innovative and competitive products and to create new jobs domestically.

Ultimately, education should become a unifying national priority that mobilizes society's intellectual and creative potential. This model of education aims to unlock the nation's historical and cultural strengths and to ensure that Uzbekistan's progress is driven by knowledge, innovation, and self-reliance rather than dependence on external labor migration.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The efforts of the country's leadership in implementing socio-economic initiatives are fundamental to Uzbekistan's sustainable development, the enhancement of public welfare, the promotion of entrepreneurship and employment, the advancement of education, the reduction of poverty, and the formation of an innovative economy. Achieving these goals requires the active involvement of all segments of society, including government institutions, public organizations, the scientific community, and local self-governance bodies.

Particular attention should be given to addressing the issue of labor migration, which remains one of the most significant challenges for Uzbekistan's socio-economic development. This problem must be approached comprehensively - not only through the creation of new jobs and the stimulation of entrepreneurship, but also by improving working conditions and expanding economic opportunities within the country.

In this regard, it is essential to develop a long-term strategy and a practical "road map" focused on the effective management of the national labor force and its gradual integration into a modern, knowledge-based economy. Such coordinated and forward-looking actions will ensure sustainable growth and contribute to the social and economic progress of Uzbekistan.

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